

TRANSLATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND ITS LEXICAL DIFFICULTIES

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***Annotation:** People in different parts of the world engross themselves in different conversations and their conversation usually evolves in English language, as it ensures that everyone can participate in debates and discussions. English language considered as an international language and serves as a communication tool between parties and politicians. Although this not only one case where people can identify English language, this language is in books of well-known authors, such as, Shakespeare, Jack London and others. While reading these books in original language without turning to translation version, one can come across phraseological expressions, idioms, colloquialisms, neologisms and etc. In order to understand such kind of above-mentioned expressions, a reader should be aware of them beforehand and be able to recognize their role and function in the text. This article will discuss the main issues of translation in terms of phraseology and common specific ways of overcoming them.*

***Keywords:** idioms, polysemantic nature, word order, Bible, Shakespearisms.*

Introduction

Since the translation field was formed many problems appeared, namely as few, grammatical, lexical, syntactic and phraseological problems, which took a lead among them, as their polysemantic nature is so complex

Phraseological unit is a set of expressions consisting from words in a fixed order, which only relates to a particular language, but not in another. Because of the language polysemantic nature, they do not have analogs in TL, these expressions cannot be translated directly in TL.

Difficulties of rendering of such expressions always begins from looking for appropriate analog in TL. There are several levels of idioms: fixed expressions by

dictionary and their fame among nations, outdated idioms but fixed in dictionary and well-known idioms only to a certain category of people.

As it was mentioned early, translator should not only pay attention to the meaning of the expressions, but also he should have a profound knowledge of language in which he translates.

There are particular rules of languages. Like Russian language has its own word order, English also has its own.

English is diverse language, and it ensures to store the same word order of English expressions, but it is not always the case. For instance: He was not present at school yesterday, in English it translates as follows: Вчера, его не было в школе. As it can be seen, the word order does not follow the same word order with Russian.

Translator should look at the following factors beforehand:

1. Being aware of existing idiomatic expressions in the ST, their function, type and its systematic role
2. Levels of understanding such expressions
3. Ways of translating them

Ways of rendering idiomatic expressions:

Finding equivalency and analog, antonymic translation, calque, descriptive translation, integral transformation and others.

Equivalents are divided into complete and partial correspondences. Complete correspondences always correlate with the same units of translating language: in semantic, grammatical structure.

Partial equivalents are identical but only to some extent, maybe with the grammar or stylistic colouring of SL.

Analogs assist translators find similar meaning of expressions, but not in the same syntax, lexis and other forms of SL

Antonymic translation convert the meaning of the SL with negative semantics in TL or transform stative form of expressions with negative or interrogative form.

Calque translation – word for word

Integral transformation come when translators struggle to find the analogs or equivalents of the original form of expressions and therefore, translator should identify what does it mean as a whole and convey their meaning to the readers

Research design, findings and analysis

According to Fedorov, «difficulties which arise during translation of phraseological expressions due to the fact, that words do not have the same meaning in terms of meaning and style in another language.»

Describing some ways of rendering phraseological units, expressions from Bible, Shakespeare's and American novels were taken as a bright example for deep analysis. It should be noted that many expressions appeared in Bible and as a result came from it. Bible was a source of replete idiomatic units. This gave a chance to the proliferation of both, Russian and English idioms.

The apple of Sodom – Содомово яблоко (**calque**)

Job's comforter- горе-утешитель (**calque**)

Shakespearisms

Shakespeare was the greatest writer in English literature. His novels and playwrights were abound of phraseological expressions

To wear heart upon sleep upon for days to peack at – душа нараспашку (**analog**)

Buy golden opinions, a word buy can be replaced with the word win – заслуживать благоприятное мнение о себе, вызывать восхищение (**equivalency**)

Statements of English writers that have become phraseological units

Not every, even very famous, author could boast that one of his statements or expressions, replenished the phraseological fund of his language. However, the process of neologization, that is, the formation of new phraseological units impossible to track or measure.

Below are just some examples of phraseological units from the 18th-20th centuries

Cool as cucumber – спокойный как огурец (**calque**)

Man Friday – assistant (**descriptive translation**)

A skeleton in the closet – тайна скрытая от посторонних глаз (**descriptive translation**)

Green like a Cheshire cat – улыбаться во все 32 зуба (**descriptive translation**)

Time is money – время – деньги (**calque**)

Discussion.

The research studied the ways of rendering idiomatic expressions. It selected several idiomatic expressions from Bible and Shakespeare as a target object for research. The findings suggest that calque way mostly utilized and it can be seen from the examples given above

Nevertheless, this research paper has numerous limitations. First, it only utilized one way of rendering idioms, which might not be considered adequate to apply the findings to a broader range of translation, because transliteration method losses clear identity of phraseological units and does not make any specific sense upon the reader. But it is still the best and common way that does not call any difficulties.

Conclusion.

To conclude it should be considered that translation of phraseological units is a troublesome process for translators. First, translators should always be aware of existing phrases in the ST and consider its function and meaning. And only then, they can handle with them by using several translation techniques, such as calque, descriptive translation equivalency and others above-mentioned.

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